

The following search string was used in Web of Science:

"TS=(("Autistic Disorder" OR "Autism Spectrum Disorder" OR "Asperger Syndrome" OR autism OR autistic OR ASD OR Asperger) AND ("Exercise" OR "Sports" OR "Exercise Therapy" OR exercise OR "physical activity" OR sport* OR "motor activity" OR "physical education") AND ("Emotional Regulation" OR emotion* OR emotional OR anxiety OR anger OR affect OR "self-regulation" OR mood OR "affect regulation" OR "impulse control" OR "emotional reactivity" OR "emotional intelligence" OR resilience) AND (random* OR trial OR "controlled study" OR "controlled trial" OR intervention OR quasi*)) NOT TS=(animals NOT humans) NOT TS=(review OR "meta-analysis" OR editorial OR letter)"*

The PubMed search incorporated MeSH terms and free-text terms, following this structure:

"(("Autistic Disorder"[15] OR "Autism Spectrum Disorder"[15] OR "Asperger Syndrome"[15] OR autism[tiab] OR autistic[tiab] OR ASD[tiab] OR Asperger[tiab]) AND ("Exercise"[15] OR "Sports"[15] OR "Exercise Therapy"[15] OR exercise[tiab] OR "physical activity"[tiab] OR sport*[tiab] OR "motor activity"[tiab] OR "physical education"[tiab]) AND ("Emotional Regulation"[15] OR emotion*[tiab] OR emotional[tiab] OR anxiety[tiab] OR anger[tiab] OR affect[tiab] OR "self-regulation"[tiab] OR mood[tiab] OR "affect regulation"[tiab] OR "impulse control"[tiab] OR "emotional reactivity"[tiab] OR "emotional intelligence"[tiab] OR resilience[tiab]) AND (random*[tiab] OR trial[tiab] OR "controlled study"[tiab] OR "controlled trial"[tiab] OR intervention[tiab] OR quasi*[tiab])) NOT (animals[15] NOT humans[15]) NOT (review[pt] OR "Meta-Analysis"[pt] OR editorial[pt] OR letter[pt])"*